

Nesting BiVO₄ nanoislands in ZnO nanodendrites by two-step electrodeposition for efficient solar water splitting

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Abstract

Photoanodes with a large electrochemically active surface area, rapid charge transfer, and broadband light harvesting capacity are required to maximize the photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting performance. To address these features, we demonstrate that 3D hierarchical ZnO nanodendrites (NDs) can be sensitized with BiVO₄ nanoislands by chemical and thermal treatments of electrodeposited Bi metal films. The flat band measurements and optical characterization suggested that the resulting heterojunction had type-II band alignment with a viable charge transfer from BiVO₄ to ZnO NDs. In parallel, PL analysis revealed inhibition of the charge recombination rate by the electron transfer between BiVO₄ and ZnO NDs. Upon AM 1.5 G illumination, BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction yielded the highest photocurrent efficiency (0.15 mA·cm⁻² at 1.2 V vs. NHE), which was attributed to its enhanced surface area (due to the presence of small dendrite branches), extended broadband light absorption extending from UV to visible light regions, and the most efficient interfacial charge transfer as proven by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies. Besides, the incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency and applied bias photon-to-current efficiency tests confirmed an improved spectral photoresponse of the heterojunction based photoanode, particularly towards the visible light spectrum. The results outline a promising synthesis route for building heterojunctions between visible light active and wide band gap semiconductors for the use as a highly efficient photoanodes in a PEC cell.

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1. Introduction

Solar energy conversion to chemical energy (i.e. hydrogen) using semiconducting materials via photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting has been regarded as efficient sustainable energy technology since the pioneering demonstration by Honda and Fujishima [1, 2]. The overpotential for water oxidation (oxygen evolution reaction (OER)) and water reduction (hydrogen evolution reaction (HER)) in this process is partially compensated by the photoinduced voltage of the light absorber [3, 4]. The semiconductor must hence possess an appropriate band alignment with the water redox potentials. The OER and HER could be driven by the PEC water splitting at potentials below 1.23 V and above 0 V with reference to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), respectively [5]. The important argument affecting the solar-to-hydrogen conversion efficiency (STH) are light absorption, charge separation/transport and surface catalytic reaction (charge transfer) [6, 7].

Many properties of semiconductor nanorods (NRs) can be significantly altered when their radial dimension (diameter) is equal or below the characteristic length of the interesting solid state phenomena such as the exciton Bohr radius, exciton diffusion length, wavelength of irradiation and phonon mean free path [8, 9]. For instance, Song *et al* fabricated a composite titania thin film composed of quasi-aligned rutile NRs embedded in anatase aggregates and its PEC behavior was significantly enhanced [10]. Recently, more efforts have been devoted on constructing three-dimensional (3D) hierarchical nanostructures from low-dimensional subunits. Compared to 1D morphologies, 3D complex zinc oxide (ZnO) morphologies present a larger active surface area, which results in a more rapid charge transfer process and water oxidation kinetics [11, 12]. This hierarchical structural design can increase the number of light transport paths and thereby improve light harvesting capacity [13, 14]. ZnO nanodendrites (NDs) included in this class of nanostructures are very promising candidate for solar energy conversion applications due to their low-cost and a facile synthesis process. In contrast to the conventional methods in which 3D ZnO NDs are grown over sequentially reseeded ZnO NRs surface in aqueous phase [15–17], Wu *et al* purposed an alternative fabrication method utilizing a supersaturated solution without any sequential seed layer or organic structure-directing agent [18]. Nevertheless, besides all other assets, a wide band gap (~ 3.2 eV) of ZnO is considered as the fundamental obstacle to achieving moderate STH efficiency via its utilization in the PEC water splitting. A novel material design is therefore needed to influence the factors mentioned above.

Photosensitization with a narrow band gap semiconductor has emerged as an effective means of extension of the optical activity of ZnO NDs into the visible region. Among the different photosensitizers that show photoactivity under visible light, monoclinic bismuth vanadate (BiVO₄) was chosen as the light absorber due to its suitable band gap (~ 2.4 eV), appreciable band edge positions for water oxidation and the matched band structure with that of ZnO [19, 20]. The monoclinic BiVO₄ alone demonstrated photocatalytic activity for the O₂ evolution from an aqueous silver nitrate solution under visible light irradiation [21, 22]. It was also reported that the formation of heterojunction photoanode between the wurtzite ZnO and monoclinic BiVO₄ promotes the charge separation and transport of electrons and holes assisted by the built-in electric field at the interface and light absorption at a wider wavelength range (UV and vis), which then boosts the PEC performance [23, 24].

In this sense, Yan *et al* reported the fabrication of ZnO NRs/BiVO₄ heterojunction through chemical bath deposition followed by successive ionic layer deposition [25]. They observed that photocurrent of ZnO NRs/BiVO₄ ($1.72 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl) was higher than that of ZnO NRs photoanode at the same potential. The improvement in photoconversion was associated with the extended spectral response towards the visible spectrum and lower recombination rate of photogenerated charge carrier. Moniz *et al* successfully synthesized 1D ZnO coupled with nanoparticulate BiVO₄ and cobalt phosphate (Co–Pi) as a hole acceptor [26]. They found that Co–Pi/BiVO₄/ZnO exhibited 12-fold increase in photocurrent ($\sim 3 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) compared to the BiVO₄. The enhancement results from higher light absorption, electron flow from BiVO₄ to ZnO, and hole transfer to Co–Pi for favorable OER. Recently, Yang and Wu constructed novel Co–Pi/BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanode based on metal organic deposition of BiVO₄ on the surface of hydrothermally grown ZnO NRs [27]. The resultant electrode yielded an optimized photocurrent density of $3.5 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 1.23 V vs. RHE after being fully depleted at a low bias potential (0.8 V vs. RHE). Along with the superior light harvesting capability and charge injection efficiency by co-catalyst Co–Pi, the authors claimed that fully depleted junction originating from thin BiVO₄ shells led to better charge transport, which in turn enhanced the PEC activity. However, synthesis techniques available to produce nanoporous morphology electrodes are quite limited. Kim and Choi presented electrochemically deposited nanoporous BiVO₄ from bismuth oxyiodide (BiOI) on fluorine-doped tin oxide substrates [28]. They suggested that the voids between 2D crystal structure of BiOI allowed the deposition of ultrathin plates (~ 20 nm) by inhibiting the grain formation of

BiVO₄ during the conversion process. Kang *et al* demonstrated that the electrodeposited Bi dendritic electrodes followed by the introduction of a V precursor solution during the oxidation process can lead to BiVO₄ NPs. The resultant BiVO₄ thin film had a high surface area and a good electrical continuity among the particles [29]. Using the similar electrodeposition procedure, Bai *et al* fabricated Cu₂O/BiVO₄ p–n heterojunction photoanode and obtained the maximum photocurrent density of 1.72 mA·cm⁻² (1.23 V vs RHE), which is 4.5 times higher than that of pristine BiVO₄ thin film (~0.38 mA·cm⁻²) at the same applied potential [30].

In view of the advantages mentioned above, herein, we introduce a facile strategy for the construction of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction photoanode with a novel nanostructure for PEC water splitting. The branches with the lengths of 300–400 nm were directly formed on hydrothermally grown primary ZnO NRs with a diameter of 84 nm in the absence of any seed layer or organic structure directing agent to produce ZnO NDs. BiVO₄ nanoislands nested in ZnO NDs were prepared by electrodeposition of Bi film followed by the introduction of V solution and thermal treatment. A two-step electrodeposition procedure generated an intimate contact at the interface between the constituent semiconductors. BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction was identified to have staggered band arrangement (type II), leading to an efficient photogenerated electron–hole separation and rapid interfacial charge transfer. Under AM 1.5 G illumination, the heterojunction photoanode achieved a higher PEC performance than the BiVO₄, ZnO NDs, and ZnO NRs photoelectrodes prepared in this study. This new approach may pave the way for rational design of heterojunctions between narrow band gap and wide band gap semiconductors with optimal structure and compositions.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Preparation of ZnO NDs photoanode

The ZnO NR arrays were synthesized by hydrothermal method. Initially, 0.8 M zinc acetate dihydrate (Zn(CH₃CO₂)₂·2H₂O, Penta) and 0.8 M diethanolamine (CH₂CH₂OH)₂NH, CDH Fine Chemicals) were dissolved in isopropanol ((CH₃)₂CHOH, Microchem), and stirred at 50 °C for 1 h. After an overnight aging, the sol was spin-coated on cleaned indium tin oxide coated (ITO, 5–15 Ω sq⁻¹, Sigma Aldrich) glass substrates at 3000 rpm for 30 s. The coated substrate was calcined in an ambient atmosphere at 400 °C for 1 h to obtain the ZnO seed layer. The typical growth solution consisting of 0.025 M zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Sigma Aldrich), 0.025 M hexamethylenetetramine ((CH₂)₆N₄, Lachner), and 0.5 ml polyethyleneimine (PEI, branched, average *M_w* ~ 800 by LS, Sigma Aldrich) was preheated for 2 h at 95 °C. The aged growth solution turned to yellow straw color. The seeded film with its conductive side facing downwards was immersed in the preheated solution (in yellow straw color) and kept at 95 °C for 6 h.

The branches of ZnO NDs were formed directly on the ZnO NRs without any assistance from another seeds and organic

structure-directing agent, as described elsewhere [31]. The ZnO NRs grown on ITO substrate were first immersed into an aqueous solution of 0.057 M zinc acetate dihydrate and 0.5 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH, Lachner) for 20 min at room temperature. During this process, the etch pits formed that served as growth centers for the formation of nanocactus (NCs), which then turned into branches after 1 h growing at 100 °C for in the same solution. The obtained ZnO NDs were carefully rinsed with deionized water and dried at 60 °C.

It should be mentioned that branch development only started from a supersaturated solution in a metastable state at a high concentration of NaOH. The supersaturation of zinc acetate and NaOH solution can be reached before the solution turns opaque after ~5 min at room temperature. Therefore, it is very important to immerse ZnO NRs in a clear solution before precipitation. A more detailed information can be found where it was primarily observed [18].

2.2. Preparation of BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanodes

Scheme 1 presents the synthesis procedure to prepare ZnO NDs coated with BiVO₄ NPs, which could be converted from electrodeposited Bi metal using a modified version of the previously described chemical and thermal treatments [29]. In the first step, the plating solution was prepared by dissolving 20 mM of bismuth(III) nitrate pentahydrate (Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O, Sigma Aldrich) in 100 ml ethylene glycol (HOCH₂CH₂OH, Sigma Aldrich) solution. The deposition was achieved by passing ~0.033 C cm⁻² at -1 V against the Ag/AgCl electrode. The other details of Bi metal electrodeposition are given in the supplementary information (figure 1S). Following that, 100 μl of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, Sigma Aldrich) containing 150 mM ammonium monovanadate (NH₄VO₃, Sigma Aldrich) was drop-casted onto the entire Bi film (area = 2 cm²) as the second step. The V precursor-incorporated film was calcined at 500 °C for 2 h in air. By thermal treatment, Bi and VO²⁺ oxidized to Bi₂O₃ and V₂O₅, which reacted to form BiVO₄. Any residual vanadium pentoxide (V₂O₅) on the electrode was removed by soaking it in 0.125 M NaOH solution for 30 s. The resultant pure BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanode was thoroughly washed by deionized water, and dried at 60 °C. For synthesis of BiVO₄, all the deposition conditions were the same, except for ITO substrates used as scaffolds.

2.3. PEC measurements

The PEC performance tests of BiVO₄ sensitized ZnO NDs were performed in three-electrode configuration within a plastic cuvette under front-side illumination at 87.5 mW·cm⁻² light intensity from a PicoTM solar simulator (G2V Optics) with a standard AM 1.5 G filter. The incident light in UV and visible regions (350–800 nm) is attenuated by 10% (data not shown) while passing throughout the PEC cell cuvette filled with electrolyte solution, corresponding that the light intensity at the sample surface was 78.75 mW·cm⁻². 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7) was used as an electrolyte solution that was

Scheme 1. Schematic representation for the fabrication of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction photoanode.

degassed by nitrogen for 10 min to remove any dissolved oxygen before the PEC measurements. The fabricated electrodes with a fixed surface area of 0.32 cm², Pt foil and Ag/AgCl (saturated with KCl) were used as the working, counter, and reference electrodes, respectively. The potentials measured vs. Ag/AgCl electrode ($E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$) were converted to normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) potentials (E_{NHE}) by using the equation:

$$E_{\text{NHE}} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.2 \text{ V.} \quad (1)$$

In linear sweep voltammograms, LSV (J-V), the scan rate was 20 mV s⁻¹ and the scan range was 0 V–1.5 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) both under dark and illuminated conditions. The incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) tests were also carried out in the three-electrode setup using 12 monochromatic channels of the solar simulator (PicoTM with AM 1.5 G filter) as the light source. The IPCE was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{IPCE} = \frac{J_{\text{ph}}(\lambda) \times 1240}{P_{\text{mono}}(\lambda) \times \lambda} \quad (2)$$

where, J_{ph} (in mA·cm⁻²) is the photocurrent density recorded under monochromatic illumination at wavelength λ (in nm), P_{mono} (in mW·cm⁻²) is the light intensity of the monochromatic source at each wavelength, the constant 1240 (hc/e in V·nm) equals to the product of Planck's constant and the speed of light divided by the charge of an electron. The applied bias photon-to-current efficiency (ABPE), analogue to the STH efficiency with no bias, was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{ABPE} = \left[\frac{J(\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}) \times (1.229 - |V_{\text{app}}|)(\text{V}) \times \eta_{\text{F}}}{P_{\text{total}}(\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2})} \right] \quad (3)$$

in which, 1.23 V is the standard state reversible potential for water splitting, V_{app} is the applied bias (measured vs. Pt), η_{F} is the Faradaic efficiency for hydrogen evolution ($\eta_{\text{F}} = 1$ in this case), and P_{total} is the intensity of the light source.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted in the same electrolyte and set-up as employed in the photocurrent measurements. The EIS data under illuminated condition was obtained at 10 mV amplitude of AC signal over a frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz. The Mott–Schottky (MS) analysis was carried out in dark at 1.5 kHz with 30 potential steps.

2.4. Characterization

The crystal structure of the samples was determined by x-ray powder diffractometry (XRD, Panalytical Empyrean DY1098) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm) under 40 kV and 45 mA in steps of 0.02°. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Nova NanoSEM 450) was employed to study the morphology of the samples. The elemental composition of the produced heterostructure was determined through energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The microstructure of the films was monitored by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEM-2100Plus, Jeol). The optical characteristics of the synthesized photoanodes were acquired by a 150 mm InGaAs integrating spheres module of a UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectrometer (Lambda 1050 Perkin Elmer). The photoluminescence spectra at room temperature were obtained by fluorescence spectrophotometer (PL, Fluorolog FL3-21, Horiba) equipped with delta diode laser DD-375 1 376 nm as an excitation source. Raman spectra were collected by a micro-Raman spectrophotometer (Renishaw in Via Reflex) at the excitation wavelength

of 532 nm. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Axis Ultra DLD spectrometer, Kratos Analytical Ltd) with a monochromatized Al $K\alpha$ radiation ($h\nu = 1,486.7$ eV), operated at 150 W (10 mA, 15 kV), was used to explore the elemental composition and oxidation states of the elements on the surface of the BiVO_4/ZnO NDs. The XPS spectra were obtained using an analysis area of $\sim 300 \mu\text{m} \times 700 \mu\text{m}$ and analyzed by Casa XPS software. Electrochemical workstation (SP-200 Potentiostat, BioLogic) with EIS was utilized to test the PEC/electrochemical performance as well as interfacial charge transfer properties of the produced electrodes.

3. Results and discussion

BiVO_4 nanoislands nested in sequential hydrothermally grown ZnO NDs was prepared by electrodeposition of Bi film followed by the introduction of V solution and thermal treatment. The amount of the decorated BiVO_4 was determined based on measuring the electrode weight before and after coating. Without contribution from ITO, the weight of ZnO NDs was determined as 0.89 mg while the weight of BiVO_4 deposits on ZnO NDs was determined as 0.12 mg, corresponding to formation of BiVO_4/ZnO NDs (~ 13.4 wt. %) heterostructure photoanode.

The XRD spectra of the produced electrodes are shown in figure 1. The peak positions of ZnO NDs are the same as those of ZnO NRs before growing ZnO branches, which correspond to the characteristic diffraction maxima of hexagonal wurtzite structure [32]. The dominant (002) peaks in the XRD patterns of ZnO NRs as well as ZnO NDs suggest a preferential orientation along the c -axis normal to the substrate rather than an anisotropic orientation. In both samples, the (002) peak at 35° with the full-width half maximum of less than 0.16° confirms a high crystallinity. An interesting aspect of this prominent peak is its stronger intensity for ZnO NDs. This change is attributed to the occurrence of branches since the crystalline volume contributes to the diffraction intensity [33]. The XRD patterns of BiVO_4 were found to be consistent with the characteristic diffraction peaks of monoclinic scheelite [34]. It is discernible that the electrodeposition of BiVO_4 did not cause any considerable peak shifting or crystal phase change of ZnO NDs. All XRD patterns of BiVO_4/ZnO NDs are therefore assigned to the co-existence of BiVO_4 and ZnO phases without any undesirable impurities. Figure 2S(a) shows the XRD patterns for ITO glass and Bi metal electrodeposited ITO glass before introducing the V precursor (DMSO containing ammonium monovanadate) to form BiVO_4 . The peak observed at 30.80° is associated with the (222) plane of ITO [35]. The peaks in the XRD pattern of Bi-deposited ITO film are indexed as the tetragonal phase of $\beta\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ [36]. The most relevant diffraction planes are labeled, and no other impurity phase was detected. The XRD results indicate that Bi metal reacts with the atmospheric oxygen to form Bi_2O_3 .

The Raman spectra of the samples are shown in figure 2. The characteristic weak peak of ZnO at 438 cm^{-1} is observed in the spectra of the ZnO NDs as well as BiVO_4/ZnO NDs.

Figure 1. XRD patterns of BiVO_4 , ZnO NRs, ZnO NDs and BiVO_4/ZnO NDs photoanodes.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of ZnO NDs, BiVO_4 , BiVO_4/ZnO NDs and BiVO_4/ZnO NDs without soaking in NaOH solution to remove V_2O_5 .

The peaks at 1090 cm^{-1} and 575 cm^{-1} are associated with the defects in ZnO crystals [37]. On the other hand, the peaks around 820 , 706 , 365 , 210 and 145 cm^{-1} in the Raman spectra of BiVO_4 and BiVO_4/ZnO NDs refer to monoclinic BiVO_4 [38], implying the formation of the crystalline BiVO_4 on ND ZnO structures. Raman spectral analysis was also applied to the as-prepared BiVO_4/ZnO NDs without soaking in NaOH solution to confirm successful removal of the residual V_2O_5 . Additional vibrational modes appeared in the Raman spectra of BiVO_4/ZnO NDs without soaking, when compared with the Raman spectra of BiVO_4/ZnO NDs. Among Raman peaks of V_2O_5 , the internal modes between $500\text{--}1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ involve V–O stretching vibrations while the external modes between $200\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ involve V–O–V bending vibrations [39]. The

Figure 3. High resolution XPS core level spectra of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs (a) Zn 2p, (b) Bi 4f, (c) V 2p and (d) O 1 s.

result indicates that the excess of V₂O₅ was firmly eliminated, and pure BiVO₄/ZnO NDs was formed.

The composition and chemical states in a BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction sample was analyzed by XPS. The peak locations in all XPS spectra were corrected using C 1 s at 284.5 eV. The high resolution XPS spectrum of Zn 2p in figure 3(a) reveals two binding energies of 1021.0 (Zn 2p_{3/2}) and 1044.0 (Zn 2p_{1/2}) eV, signifying that Zn is present in the Zn²⁺ state [40]. The typical binding energies of 158.0 (Bi 4f_{7/2}) and 163.4 (Bi 4f_{5/2}) eV in figure 3(b) denote Bi in the 3+ state. As for the V 2p XPS spectrum in figure 3(c), the major peaks appeared at 515.7 (V 2p_{3/2}) and 523.5 eV (V 2p_{1/2}) indicate that V in BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanode is present in the oxidation state of V⁵⁺ [41]. Figure 3(d) demonstrates the O 1 s core level spectrum with two deconvoluted peaks at 529.7 and 531.7 eV. The peak located at 529.7 eV is mainly attributed to the lattice oxygen of ZnO crystal while the peak located at 531.7 eV is related to the hydroxyl (–OH) groups formed on the surface of specimen [42].

Cross-sectional and top-view SEM images and diameter distribution of the primarily grown ZnO NR are respectively shown in supporting information (figures 3S(a)–(c)). Growth of vertically aligned ZnO NRs on a 300 nm thick seed layer after 6 h during the hydrothermal synthesis resulted in homogeneous hexagonal arrays with a length of ~2 μm and an

average diameter of 44 nm. Moreover, the spines grew directly on the ZnO NRs to form the NCs at room temperature after 20 min (figure 3S(d)). As shown in figure 4(a), SEM image demonstrates that the spines developed into the branches to form ZnO NDs with high surface area after subsequent hydrothermal growth at 100 °C for 1 h. These branches lengths ranged from 300 to 400 nm. The diameter distribution of the primary ZnO NRs within NDs is shown in figure 4(b), demonstrating that the average diameter increased from 44 nm to 84 nm. It should be pointed out that the electrodeposited Bi crystals did not cover the entire ITO surface (figure 2S(b)). This island morphology of Bi is attributed to the poor dissolution of Bi deposits [28, 29]. However, as shown in figure 4(c), the ITO surface was almost fully covered with porous, uniform, and nanocrystalline BiVO₄. After introducing V source and after heat treatment, the morphology of BiVO₄ altered significantly compared to that of the original Bi metal deposits. The SEM image of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction shown in figure 4(d) illustrates that electrodeposition process successfully nested BiVO₄ nanoislands in and on top of ZnO NDs. The size of the BiVO₄ nanostructures was about 200–300 nm. It should be noted that there is a difference in appearance between the growth orientation of BiVO₄ NPs on planar ITO and 3D complex ZnO structures. In the former, the nanoparticles accumulate laterally, in the latter, there is

Figure 4. SEM images of (a) ZnO NDs, (b) corresponding diameter distribution of ZnO NDs, (c) BiVO₄, and (d) BiVO₄/ZnO NDs.

a vertical growth of the porous small nanoparticles stacked on top of each other appear like a single large cluster. The quality of semiconductor-semiconductor contact is essential for achieving excellent PEC performance of the heterojunction device. BiVO₄ nanoislands in the upper layer tightly wrap ZnO NDs and intertwine them, leading to an intimate contact at the interface for the expected good charge separation. Electrodeposition occurs on a conductive substrate by facilitating electrons for the reaction. It was reported that ZnO NRs displayed polarity dependent high electrical conductivity varying between 10.2 and 90.9 S cm⁻¹ [43]. This value is much smaller than the electrical conductivity of ITO substrate that is $\sim 10^4$ S cm⁻¹ [44]. Equally important is the electrical conductivity of the electrodeposited compounds. Electrons cannot easily reach all the locations at the deposits for the low conductivity phase while electrons are available at all the surface sites for the high conductivity phase [45]. To emphasize again, the cathodic current during the electrodeposition of Bi metal on ZnO reached as high as -1.1 mA, signifying sufficient electrical conductivity of electrodeposited phase. Our results suggest that ZnO in the form of branched NRs provides suitable electrical and transport properties for the uniform formation of BiVO₄ NPs via electrodeposited Bi metal. Besides, ZnO NDs slightly corroded due to the immersion in the acidic Bi metal plating solution for 5 min.

The EDX analysis of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs (figure 4S) reveals that the heterostructure is only composed of zinc, bismuth, vanadium, and oxygen. The absence of any other element confirms the purity of the fabricated film.

Figure 5. TEM image of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction.

Figure 5 represents the TEM image of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterostructure extracted from a large area of ND arrays. ZnO NDs slightly corroded during the electrodeposition of Bi metal film due to the acidity of the plating solution as

Figure 6. (a) PL spectra (excitation wavelength 335 nm, the peak at 670 nm corresponds to its second harmonics), (b) Absorption plus scattering spectra ($A + S = 100 - R - T$), (c) Nyquist plots under AM 1.5 G irradiation and (d) Mott-Schottky plot of BiVO₄ and ZnO NDs semiconductors.

was also observed by SEM. The surface morphology examination indicates that a branch grew vertically from the stem of primary ZnO NRs, which have a diameter of about ~65 nm. Moreover, the size of BiVO₄ crystals is about ~200 nm with relatively darker contrast. It can also be deduced that BiVO₄ nanoislands are firmly bound to ZnO NDs, leading to a good electrical continuity between two phases. All these results are consistent with SEM observations.

The semiconductor heterojunction photoanode is reportedly very effective for improvement of the interfacial charge transportation and separation efficiency [23, 46]. To evaluate the recombination rate within the fabricated photoelectrodes PL measurements were performed under the excitation wavelength of 335 nm as its qualitative indication. As seen from figure 6(a), two distinctive emission peaks appeared in the PL spectra of ZnO NRs, ZnO NDs and BiVO₄/ZnO NDs. The peak at 376 nm results from the near band edge (NBE) transitions in ZnO [47]. Another wide and intense emission peak for the pristine ZnO samples appeared at 570 nm and was associated with the presence of the oxygen vacancies [48]. As BiVO₄ deposits on ZnO NDs, a red-shift of the defect-induced emission is observed at 620 nm. Annealing ZnO increases the amount of the oxygen interstitials and decreases the amount of the oxygen vacancies [49]. Therefore, this shift of visible emission could be related to the variation of the local surroundings of the defect sites as a result of annealing the heterojunction sample. In the case of BiVO₄, two broad peaks

at 505 and 410 nm were attributed to the NBE transition and the deep level defects, respectively [50]. In fact, high PL intensity generally characterizes a high recombination rate of the photogenerated charge carrier [51]. The ZnO NDs NBE emission intensity shows a remarkable reduction after coating it with BiVO₄. Consequently, it can be stated that the formation of heterojunction between BiVO₄ NPs and ZnO NDs can significantly inhibit the recombination rate and decrease the number of crystal defects. The efficiency of charge separation plays a vital role regarding the PEC properties.

UV-vis spectrophotometry was also carried out to study the light absorption capacity of the ZnO electrodes associated with the structural transformation and BiVO₄ photosensitization. Absorption and scattering spectra ($A + S = 100 - R - T$) of the samples were calculated by subtracting reflectance (figure 5S(a)) and transmittance (figure 5S(b)) from 100% incident light and illustrated in figure 6(b). Among the electrodes, the most significant non-zero baseline ($\lambda > 400$ nm) was observed for ZnO NDs. The main reason is that the horizontally aligned dense branches surrounding the primary NRs cause scattering. Most photons pass directly through the ITO substrate where they may be internally reflected or escape unmeasured (light loss) [52]. The superior light absorption emerging from structural evolution of the branched ZnO nanostructures was reported previously and justified in a similar way [12, 33]. The spectra also indicate that ZnO NRs and ZnO NDs have very similar UV absorption edges at 380 nm while the absorption edge of

the pure BiVO₄ appears at 550 nm. The band gap (E_g) of ZnO NDs and BiVO₄ was respectively determined to be 3.2 eV and 2.3 eV through Kubelka–Munk transformation (figure 5S(c)), indicating that the optical response from BiVO₄ in the visible region and from ZnO NDs in the UV region effectively contribute to the absorption spectrum of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs, manifesting high potential as photoanode with ~55% solar irradiance exploitation capacity.

Figure 6(c) shows the EIS response under illumination in the form of Nyquist plots for all electrodes. The semi-circular arc of the Nyquist plot represents the interfacial charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), referring to the electron transfer kinetics at the electrode/electrolyte interface. The R_{ct} values were obtained by the equivalent Randle circuit (figure 6(c) inset). The R_{ct} values of ZnO NRs, ZnO NDs, BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/ZnO NDs were 147, 95, 164 and 52 k Ω , respectively. The branches occupy the void space between the primary NRs and generate more intimate contact at the ZnO NDs electrode/electrolyte interface. The increased electrochemically active surface area results in a relatively lower R_{ct} of ZnO NDs as compared to ZnO NRs. Correlating with PL analysis, these results also confirm that the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterostructure has the most rapid charge transfer with the lowest resistance, which is desirable for efficient PEC performance. EIS results measured both under dark and illuminated conditions are shown in the supporting information (figure 6S) and indicate the semiconducting nature of the photoelectrode samples upon illumination.

MS analysis was carried out to analyze the intrinsic electronic structures of the BiVO₄ and ZnO NDs by measuring the space charge capacitance of the semiconductors at various applied potentials. The slope and the intercept to the x -axis of MS plots gives the donor density (N_D) and the flat band potential (V_{fb}) according to equation:

$$\frac{1}{C_s^2} = \frac{2}{e\epsilon_r\epsilon_0 N_d A^2} \left(V_{app} - V_{fb} - \frac{kT}{e} \right) \quad (4)$$

where C_s , e , ϵ_r , ϵ_0 , A , V_{app} , k and T are the space charge layer capacitance, the elementary electric charge, the dielectric constant of the semiconductors, the permittivity of the vacuum, the surface area of the working electrode, the applied potential, the Boltzmann constant, and the temperature, respectively. As can be seen in figure 6(d), both pristine photoelectrodes are the n -type semiconductors with positive slopes in the MS plots. The V_{fb} of ZnO NDs was estimated to be 0.123 V (vs NHE at pH 7) or -0.077 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The V_{fb} of BiVO₄ was estimated to be -0.070 V (vs NHE at pH 7) or -0.270 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The V_{fb} for BiVO₄ lies between -0.7 V and -0.3 V (vs Ag/AgCl) in a pH range of 5.8–7 while the V_{fb} for ZnO lies between -0.29 V and -0.2 V (vs Ag/AgCl) at pH 7.4 [53]. In our study, both estimated V_{fb} values under almost identical conditions are in a good agreement with those reported in the literature. The N_D of ZnO NDs and BiVO₄ was estimated to be 0.18×10^{20} (cm⁻³) and 0.91×10^{19} (cm⁻³), respectively. It should be emphasized that N_D values deduced from MS plots do not correspond to the absolute concentration as the model is proposed for the planar system [54]. However, this analysis

could signify a qualitative trend in donor density and flat band potential values of the studied semiconductors. Besides, these values strongly depend on the measurement conditions such as the frequency and the pH of electrolyte solution.

The conduction band maxima (E_{CBM}) and the valence band minima (E_{VBM}) of the two semiconductors in the heterostructure were also calculated by the following equations:

$$E_{CBM} = E_F - kT \ln \left(\frac{N_D}{N_C} \right) \text{ and } E_{VBM} = E_{CBM} - E_g. \quad (5)$$

Here, $E_F = -eV_{fb}$ is the Fermi level and $N_C = \left(\frac{2m_h^* kT}{h^2} \right)^{3/2}$ is the effective density of states in the conduction band where $m_h^* = 0.24 m_0$ for ZnO [55] and $m_h^* = 0.28 m_0$ for BiVO₄ [56]. The exact position of the band edges is specified with respect to the vacuum level on the energy scale. The NHE is located at -4.5 eV (at 298.15 K) compared to the vacuum level. Accordingly, the E_{CBM} and the E_{VBM} of the ZnO NDs were found to lie at -7.57 eV and -4.37 eV (vs vacuum at pH 7), respectively. On the other hand, the E_{CBM} and the E_{VBM} of the BiVO₄ were measured to be -6.67 eV and -4.10 eV (vs vacuum at pH 7), respectively. These values are comparable to the previously reported values for ZnO [57] and BiVO₄ [58] photoanodes. Considering the fundamentals of heterojunction formation, it is inferred that the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs form a typical staggered alignment (type-II heterojunction) [59], suggesting the viability of the electrons transfer from BiVO₄ to ZnO.

Figure 7(a) shows the linear sweep voltammetry curves of ZnO NRs, ZnO NDs, BiVO₄ and BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanode samples under AM 1.5 G illumination (87.5 mW·cm⁻²), including the dark scan. A negligible photocurrent density was observed during the dark scan. The photocurrent of ZnO NRs reached saturation around 0.5 V while the photocurrent of pristine BiVO₄ continuously increased with increasing applied potential. ZnO NDs and BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanodes exhibited almost similar I - V characteristics, which partially saturated around 0.7 V but still moderately continued increasing with increasing applied potential. This relatively higher saturated photocurrent was associated with the improved charge transport (lower charge transfer resistance) within the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs hybrid anode through branches as direct pathways for photogenerated holes towards electrolyte [60, 61]. At 1.2 V vs NHE, the photocurrent density of the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs, ZnO NDs, BiVO₄, and ZnO NRs photoanodes are respectively 0.15, 0.10, 0.06, 0.03 mA·cm⁻². The improved photocurrent density of ZnO NDs compared to ZnO NRs is associated with its large surface area. Among all the photoanodes, BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction photoanode prepared using the two-step electrodeposition procedure for the formation of BiVO₄ nanoislands demonstrated the highest photocurrent density. As indicated by the used characterization studies, the observed significant enhancement in PEC efficiency is attributed to the following factors: the extended light absorption due to narrow band gap BiVO₄ sensitization; the

Figure 7. (a) LSV curves, (b) IPCE spectra measured at 1.2 V vs NHE and (c) ABPE spectra of the different photoanodes; and (d) photostability measurement of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction photoanode at an applied bias of 1.2 V vs NHE.

inhibition of charge recombination after heterojunction formation; the improved charge transfer/transportation as a result of ZnO morphological evolution from NRs to NDs.

To investigate the PEC activity in the visible light, the LSV curve of the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs was also recorded under AM 1.5 G irradiation with a UV filter with a 420 nm cut-off wavelength. As presented in figure 7(a), the photocurrent density of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs without contribution from UV region is 0.145 mA·cm⁻². This also supports the hypothesis that favorable electron transfer from the conduction band of BiVO₄ to conduction band of ZnO NDs occurs via visible light absorption.

The IPCE spectra was measured at 1.2 V vs. NHE to elucidate the spectral light response of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction as compared to pristine BiVO₄, ZnO NRs, and ZnO NDs, as shown in figure 7(b). In the UV region, the IPCE of ZnO NDs was up to 12%, which was two and three times higher than those of BiVO₄ (6%) and ZnO NRs (4%), respectively. In line with the optical absorption spectra, the IPCE of both ZnO electrodes around 400 nm is almost zero, whereas the IPCE of BiVO₄ extended up to 520 nm. The BiVO₄/ZnO NDs yielded broadband photoresponse from 360 nm to 520 nm as a result of the coupling narrow band gap of BiVO₄ with the wide band gap of ZnO. The ABPE spectra of the produced photoanodes calculated from I–V curves (figure 7(a)) are plotted in figure 7(c). The BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterostructure displayed the highest ABPE, which is about 1.5, 3.6 and 5 times higher

than those of ZnO NDs, BiVO₄, and ZnO NDs, respectively. The maximum ABPE was achieved at the potentials of 0.55, 0.53, 0.43, and 0.80 for BiVO₄/ZnO NDs, ZnO NDs, ZnO NRs, and BiVO₄, respectively. The IPCE and ABPE results are in good agreement with the PEC performance ranking of the fabricated electrodes, suggesting that the practical Faradaic efficiency for H₂ evolution for the heterojunction would also be markedly enhanced.

The photostability curve of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction for a period of 30 min is given in figure 7(d). The photocurrent density of the photoelectrode decreased by 56% in 900 s. In the rest of the curve, the photocurrent density reduction was further reduced by 8% with a relatively more stable behavior and reached totally up to 64% under irradiation at an applied potential of 1.2 V vs NHE in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄. To gain further insight into the reason of the significant reduction in the photocurrent, SEM image of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs photoanode after photostability test is displayed in figure 8. It is interesting to realize that the primarily grown ZnO NRs became severely thinner after 30 min due to the fast degradation in alkaline solution. It is also clearly shown that several parts of the hybrid thin film are missing because of complete separation of ZnO NRs from seed layer on ITO substrate, leading to the formation of regional cavities. Compared to SEM image before the PEC measurements (figure 4(d)), BiVO₄ NPs retained their structural integrity to some extent but already appear smaller and discrete on ZnO NDs after 30 min of continuous operation.

Figure 8. SEM image of BiVO₄/ZnO NDs after the photostability test for 30 min under AM 1.5 G illumination at 1.2 V vs NHE.

However, they were observed to be more resilient to corrosion than ZnO. As a result, most of the reduction in photocurrent was determined to be majorly associated with the removal of ZnO NDs from ITO and the partial solvation of BiVO₄ NPs in the electrolyte solution, which is taking advantage of the visible light of the solar irradiation. A similar photocorrosion response of BiVO₄ coated ZnO NRs operated under almost same conditions (at 1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl in 0.5 M Na₂SO₄) was reported by Yan *et al* [25].

The schematic energy diagram of the band alignment of the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction with the PEC mechanism is proposed according to the estimation of band edges of BiVO₄ and ZnO NDs (from Mott–Schottky and optical absorption measurements) in scheme 2. Upon AM 1.5 G irradiation, the photogenerated electrons in the CB of BiVO₄ flow through the CB of the ZnO, because the CB of BiVO₄ was found to lie at a more negative potential (relative to the vacuum) than the CB of ZnO. The accumulated electrons at the CB of the ZnO NDs are then pulled towards the Pt electrode through the conductive ITO substrate to drive the HER. In the meantime, the photogenerated holes at the VB of ZnO migrate and accumulate at the VB of BiVO₄ to drive the OER. It is worth noting that ZnO NDs are still in contact with the electrolyte solution (figure 4(d)): a majority of the energetic photogenerated holes are thus likely extracted for OER. Overall, the type-II staggered alignment within BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction stems from the VB of BiVO₄ with high density of accumulated holes and the CB of ZnO NDs with high density of accumulated electrons. As confirmed by PL and EIS

studies, this band edge arrangement can remarkably promote the charge separation (low recombination rate) and the interfacial charge transfer/transportation, which lead to the efficient PEC performance for the novel BiVO₄ electrodeposited ZnO NDs.

Table 1 shows a comparison of photocurrent for various BiVO₄/ZnO photoelectrodes prepared in previous reports. Several studies revealed that BiVO₄/ZnO nanostructures achieve better PEC response compared to the pristine form of the constituent semiconductors [62, 63]. The reported photocurrent values in the literature are varying in a wide range from 0.07 mA·cm⁻² [64] to 1.72 mA·cm⁻² [25] depending on the used modification method. The majority of the tabulated heterostructures [5, 26, 27] with relatively higher photocurrent values have also been modified by the Co-Pi co-catalyst, which efficiently suppresses surface charge recombination and leads to higher photocurrent density. A systematic analogy of the values obtained in our work with the other values in the literature where AM 1.5 G irradiation was employed in measurements is not very evidentiary because of the inaccuracy of the simulated solar irradiance, particularly at the wavelengths below 365 nm [65], and the not common use of experimental conditions such as electrolyte solution. In this work, BiVO₄ nanoislands nested in ZnO NDs with primary NRs diameter of 84 nm and branch length of 300–400 nm was prepared without any co-catalyst modification. The PEC performance of the produced samples have been tested in a home-made PEC cell. BiVO₄/ZnO nanocomposite photoanode generated a reproducible higher photocurrent than the

Scheme 2. The estimated band edge alignment within BiVO₄/ZnO NDs heterojunction photoanode indicating feasible charge transfer and PEC mechanism under AM 1.5 G illumination.

Table 1. Comparison of the PEC performance of BiVO₄/ZnO nanostructured photoanodes modified by different methods.

Heterojunction Photoanode and Ref.	Modification method	Light source	Electrolyte	Photocurrent density
CoPi/BiVO ₄ /ZnO nanodendrites [27]	Metal organic decomposition	AM1.5 g simulated sunlight at 100 mW·cm ⁻²	0.3 M Na ₂ SO ₄ with potassium phosphate at pH 7.5	3.5 mA·cm ⁻² at 1.23 V vs RHE
1D-ZnO nanorods/BiVO ₄ [64]	Wet chemical reaction	A 150 W Xe light at 100 mW·cm ⁻²	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ at pH 7	0.07 mA·cm ⁻² at 0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl
Dual layer BiVO ₄ /ZnO [53]	Co-precipitation	Xe lamp with AM1.5 at 100 mW·cm ⁻²	1 M NaOH	3.5 mA·cm ⁻² at 1.2 V vs RHE
1D ZnO/BiVO ₄ [25]	Silar	Xe lamp at 100 mW·cm ⁻²	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	1.72 mA·cm ⁻² at 1.2 V vs Ag/AgCl
3D-Bicontinuous BiVO ₄ /ZnO with CoPi [5]	Metal organic decomposition	Xe lamp with AM1.5	0.2 M Na ₂ SO ₄ at pH 6.5	3.4 mA·cm ⁻² at 0.6 V vs RHE
1D Co-Pi Modified BiVO ₄ /ZnO [26]	Spray pyrolysis	Xenon lamp at 75 mW·cm ⁻²	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	3 mA·cm ⁻² at 1.2 V vs RHE
In this study	Electrodeposition	Solar simulator with AM1.5 g at 87.5 mW·cm ⁻²	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	0.15 mA·cm ⁻² at 1.2 V vs NHE

other produced electrodes. The use of electrodeposition facilitates a good control over the deposition thickness and deposit characteristics. Nevertheless, the major obstacle in producing Bi layer by electroplating solution is the insolubility of the Bi(III) salts unless the solution is strongly acidic. The semiconductor of interest to form heterojunction with BiVO₄ must be robust in strong acidic aqueous solutions. Therefore, further research activities are needed to develop moderate conditions for electrodeposition of Bi metal on ZnO NDs to ensure maximum sunlight utilization during PEC water splitting.

4. Conclusion

In summary, the BiVO₄/ZnO NDs nanostructure was successfully produced via a facile combination of hydrothermal method without secondary seed layer and Bi metal film electrodeposition followed by the introduction of V precursor solution and thermal treatment. The Bi deposition on ZnO NDs with good adhesion and coverage was achieved after 5 min at -1 V vs. Ag/AgCl electrode. Through flat band and optical measurements, it was determined that BiVO₄/ZnO NDs have type II band alignment, allowing photogenerated electron

transfer from BiVO₄ to ZnO, and vice versa for photogenerated holes. As a result, the BiVO₄/ZnO heterojunction photoanode exhibited the highest photocurrent (0.15 mA·cm⁻² at 1.2 V vs. NHE), which is 1.5, 2.5 and 5 times higher than that of ZnO NDs, BiVO₄, ZnO NRs photoanodes produced in this study. The significant advancement in photocurrent efficiency of the heterojunction photoanode produced in this study was associated with several factors: (1) enhanced light absorption towards the visible light region (due to narrow band gap of 2.3 eV for BiVO₄); (2) favorable charge transfer confirmed by lower interfacial charge transfer resistance (thinner branches around NRs endows larger contact area between electrode/electrolyte); (3) suppression of charge recombination rate, thus more efficient charge separation. The electrodeposition of primary metal layer to convert into visible light absorber material is a feasible approach to sensitize photoanode materials with poor light absorption. On this basis, the current work can be expanded to fabricate various highly efficient heterostructured photoanodes for use in PEC water splitting and other solar energy applications.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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